

Statistical problems in a meta-analysis on vitamin C and critically ill patients by Putzu (2019)

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These comments were originally published in PubPeer, 2019 July:

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/31E6DF677EC5A16CFBD1908ADACD15#1>

to which Giovanni Landoni responded in PubPeer

and at the end of this document is a comment on that response, 2019 August:

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/31E6DF677EC5A16CFBD1908ADACD15#3>

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Comment on:

Putzu A, Daems AM, Lopez-Delgado JC, Giordano VF, Landoni G.

The effect of vitamin C on clinical outcome in critically ill patients: A systematic review with meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials.

Crit Care Med. 2019;47(6):774-783.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30839358>

<https://doi.org/10.1097/ccm.00000000000003700>

<https://doi.org/10.5167/uzh-180606>

An important goal in modern biomedicine is specificity. The strength of the RCT is that the difference between the trial groups can be specifically attributed to the intervention that is being tested.

The title of a recent review in Critical Care Medicine by Putzu et al. indicated that their focus was the specific effect of vitamin C for critically ill patients (1). The abstract describes that they “included randomized controlled trials on the use of vitamin C (any regimen) in adult critically ill patients versus placebo or no therapy”, though the reader does not know what the “any regimen” means in the context. However, Table 1 of the review shows that only five of the 16 included ICU trials were vitamin C trials. Eleven of the included ICU trials administered vitamin C together with vitamins A, B, or E, or with selenium, zinc, etc. Thus, those 11 trials do not test the specific effect of vitamin C on ICU patients. The other substances can have negative or positive effects of their own, biasing the analysis of vitamin C effects. In the field of meta-analysis, combining results of trials which are too different, is referred to as the apples and oranges problem.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

The Putzu et al. meta-analyses (1) estimated the effect of vitamin C on continuous outcomes by using the standardized mean difference (SMD) scale, which uses the standard deviation (SD) as the unit of the scale. In their abstract, Putzu et al. stated erroneously that in cardiac surgery patients vitamin C decreased the length of ICU stay by 0.28 days (1), whereas **the correct statement is that ICU stay was reduced by 0.28 SD units. However, the unit of SD is incomprehensible to most readers.**

The Cochrane Handbook, for example, discourages use of the SMD scale: “... *the method assumes that the differences in standard deviations among studies reflect differences in measurement scales and not real differences in variability among study populations. This assumption may be problematic in some circumstances where we expect real differences in variability between the participants in different studies... The overall intervention effect can also be difficult to interpret as it is reported in units of standard deviation rather than in units of any of the measurement scales used in the review*” (2: sect 9.2.3.2).

Putzu et al. also included some trials twice. In subgroup analysis 2.1.2 of eFigure 8, Putzu includes both the Sadeghpour (3) and the Moludi (4) trials. Both were carried out at Rajaie Cardiovascular Medical and Research Center at Iran University of Medical Sciences. Both had 290 patients, with 113 vitamin C participants and 177 control participants, and with 191 men and 99 women (3,4). In both reports the duration of intubation was 11.8 hours in the vitamin C group and 14.14 hours in the control group, and in both the incidence of post-operative atrial fibrillation was 35% in the vitamin C group and 55% in the control group (3,4). There are two authors in common for both trial reports and it seems evident that the Moludi (4) report is a Farsi translation of the English report by Sadeghpour (3). Thus, **Putzu counted the same trial twice.**

In subgroup analysis 2.4.2 of eFigure 9, Putzu includes both the Alshafey (5) and the Retz (6) trials. Putzu does not give a reference to either trial in their reference list (1). However, eTable 6 indicates that both trials were published in “*Journal of the Egyptian Society of Cardio-Thoracic Surgery*”, though the author of the latter trial is written as Rezk in eTable 6. Search of that journal identifies the Alshafey (5) trial but no separate Retz/Rezk (6) trial. The only vitamin C paper in that journal by Rezk as an author is the Alshafey (5) trial where Rezk is a co-author. Furthermore, in the subgroup analysis both trials have 50 participants in the vitamin C and placebo groups. In both trials the length of ICU stay was 2.78 days in the vitamin C group and 3.58 days in the control group with identical SD values. Evidently, **a single trial is also included twice in this case.**

It is common for results from a trial to be reported in separate forums, however a trial should only be included once in a meta-analysis. For example, the Cochrane Handbook instructs: “*Studies are frequently reported in more than one publication (Tramèr 1997, von Elm 2004). However, the unit of interest in a Cochrane Intervention review is the study and not the report. Thus, information from multiple reports needs to be collated*”(2: sect 7.6.4). It seems that Putzu et al. did not follow such guidance.

We undertook our own meta-analysis of vitamin C for critically ill patients and found 17 controlled trials that were informative about the specific effect of vitamin C on the length of ICU stay (7). Restricting our analysis to 12 trials with 1766 patients, we calculated that vitamin C reduced the length of ICU stay by 7.8% ($p = 0.00003$). We calculated the effect of vitamin C on the relative scale, since there is strong evidence that the relative scale better captures the effects on duration (7,8,9).

In their abstract, Putzu et al. write that “*in a mixed population of ICU patients, vitamin C administration is associated with no significant effect on ... length of ICU or hospital stay*” (1).

However, our review shows that restricting the analysis to trials of vitamin C alone, carrying out the search thoroughly, and using the relative scale can lead to very different conclusions about the effects of vitamin C on the length of ICU stay (7).

References

1. Putzu A, Daems AM, Lopez-Delgado JC, Giordano VF, Landoni G. The effect of vitamin C on clinical outcome in critically ill patients: a systematic review with meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Crit Care Med* 2019;47:774–83.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30839358>
<https://doi.org/10.1097/CCM.0000000000003700>
2. Cochrane Handbook. Sections 7.6.4 and 9.2.3.2.
<https://handbook-5-1.cochrane.org>
<https://www.cochrane.org/authors/handbooks-and-manuals/handbook/archive/v5.1.0>
3. Sadeghpour A, Alizadehasl A, Kyavar M, et al. Impact of vitamin C supplementation on post-cardiac surgery ICU and hospital length of stay. *Anesth Pain Med* 2015;5:e25337.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4350190>
4. Moludi J, Keshavarz S, Pakzad R, et al. Effect of vitamin C supplementation in the prevention of atrial fibrillation. *Tehran Univ Med J* 2016;73:791–7.
<http://tumj.tums.ac.ir/article-1-7191-en.html>
5. Alshafey MK, Elrakhawy HM, Rezk ME, Moustafa HM. Role of ascorbic acid in reduction of the incidence of the atrial fibrillation in patients under beta-blocker and undergoing coronary artery bypass graft operation in early post-operative period. *J Egyptian Soc Cardio-Thoracic Surgery* 2017;25:198-203.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jescts.2017.04.003>
6. Retz (cited in 2.4.2 of eFigure 9 of ref 1. without any details of the reference; apparently a duplicate of ref. 5).
7. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C can shorten the length of stay in the ICU: a meta-analysis. *Nutrients* 2019;11:708.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30934660>
<https://doi.org/10.3390/nu11040708>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6521194>
8. Friedrich, JO, Adhikari NK, Beyene J. Ratio of means for analyzing continuous outcomes in meta-analysis performed as well as mean difference methods. *J Clin Epidemiol* 2011;64:556–64.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21447428>
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2010.09.016>
9. Hemilä H. Duration of the common cold and similar continuous outcomes should be analyzed on the relative scale: a case study of two zinc lozenge trials. *BMC Med Res Methodol* 2017;17:82.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28494765>
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-017-0356-y>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5427521>
10. Hemilä H, Pirinen M. Estimating quantile treatment effect on the original scale of the outcome variable: a case study of common cold treatments. *Trials*. 2025 Nov 24;26(1):541.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/41286897>
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-025-09265-z>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC12645726>

Response to the above criticism by

Prof. Giovanni Landoni, MD and Dr. Alessandro Putzu, MD

See their PubPeer response to the above criticism:

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/31E6DF677EC5A16CFBD1908ADACD15#2>

This is comment on Landoni and Putzu's response.

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<https://pubpeer.com/publications/31E6DF677EC5A16CFBD1908ADACD15#3>

Drs. Landoni and Putzu write about the Sadeghpour and Moludi trials: “*The endpoints of the studies were also different (Sadeghpour trial: length of hospital and ICU stay; Moludi trial: postoperative atrial fibrillation)*”. However, this is not correct. [bold added below]

Moludi et al write in their Abstract: “*the two groups were compared in terms of the following: Atrial and ventricular arrhythmias after surgery, **ICU stay and hospital stay** and duration of intubation.*”

<http://tumj.tums.ac.ir/article-1-7191-en.html>

Sadeghpour et al. write in their Methods: “*All the patients were monitored in the open heart ICU before their transfer to a ward. Data such as bypass time and cross-clamp time were collected intraoperatively. Additionally, information was gathered in the ICU on the total length of ICU stay, intubation time, drainage volume and presence of some complications (mortality and morbidity) defined as death, any infection, any impairment in the renal function and need for reoperation. Finally, the total duration of hospital stay was recorded for every individual.*”

In the Results section, they also report “*the overall incidence rate of **postoperative AF** [atrial fibrillation]*” which means that they collected data also for that specific outcome.

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4350190>

It is misleading to claim that the endpoints of the studies were different. They were extensively overlapping.

Furthermore, Drs. Landoni and Putzu do not have any kinds of proposals how two independent studies might have identical numbers of males and females, and vitamin C and placebo participants, and identical duration of intubation in the study groups, and identical incidence of post-operative AF in the study groups. Such extensive identity in the figures makes it most likely that the Moludi reports is simply a Farsi translation of the Sadeghpour reports, as I proposed.

Drs. Landoni and Putzu also write that “*as we anticipated a low number of studies administering only vitamin C, we chose to include those studies administering vitamin C in combination with other drugs as well.*” Multi-substance treatments can be investigated. However, we cannot draw a conclusion that the effect of a multi-substance intervention is caused by vitamin C specifically. Claiming that “*studies administering vitamin C in combination with other drugs*” informs us about specific effects of vitamin C misleads the readers.